

Ride 2Rail

D4.2 MONITORING INDICATORS AND TARGETS

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1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The purpose of this deliverable is to specify the Key Performance Indicators (KPI) and associated targets that will be used to evaluate the RIDE2RAIL project. These KPIs ensure that the performance of RIDE2RAIL (R2R) during demonstration activities is fully and appropriately monitored. These KPIs then inform the calculation of impact as specified within Work Package 5. The harmonisation of clear KPIs in a systematic manner means that KPIs can be tailored to the specific circumstances and aims of a given demonstrator site, while, as a set across the four partner sites, provide a holistic picture of RIDE2RAIL impact.

The deliverable presents background information and the overall roadmap of WP4 activities, of which this deliverable constitutes the second achievement, the main objectives of this deliverable and overall approach taken. The deliverable then describes the definition of common characteristics and requirements of good quality Key Performance Indicators, and describes the methodology used to elicit and define monitoring indicators and targets. This is a combination of analysis of project needs as expressed in the Description of Work, and demonstration partner needs and expectations as presented in D4.1. This generated a set of potential KPIs that were harmonised and then presented to demo partners for confirmation and target setting, followed by a final round of harmonisation.

The initial round of harmonisation identified a similar set of KPIs across the demo sites. However there was variation in the units of analysis (e.g. passengers per day, per year, in total for the demo duration). Also, there were some targets and measures that were closer to impact (i.e. calculations of the overall benefits of RIDE2RAIL) as opposed to directly measurable metrics within the demo. The scope was therefore set that only directly measurable metrics should be included in KPIs. Also, KPIs were identified at different levels:

- Whole project KPIs – KPI types and targets for all of the demo sites combined
- Cross Demo KPIs – KPI types that matched whole project KPIs, but with local targets
- Local KPIs – KPIs that were relevant to only one demo site

This first harmonisation was presented to demo sites in bilateral discussion. The result is six whole project / cross demo Key Performance Indicators that align with both the demo description of KPIs in D4.1 and serve to inform the impact analysis that will be conducted as Task 5.4. These are:

- KPI#1 Number of R2R app users
- KPI#2 Number of completed R2R app trips
- KPI#3 Number of completed multi-occupancy vehicle trips with R2R app
- KPI#4 Number of completed trips involving public transit/rail with R2R app
- KPI#5 Number of completed commuter trips with R2R app
- KPI#6 Number of completed rural trips with R2R app
- KPI#7 Number of R2R app downloads

Additional local KPIs were identified for Athens, Brno and Helsinki.

The deliverable presents targets for KPIs, along with commentary on gaps identified in demo site discussion, and on the KPIs inform subsequent tasks and deliverables. This deliverable does not define how to measure the KPIs – this will be specified in T5.1 and D5.1. However, example approaches are offered in this deliverable.

Abbreviations and acronyms

D	Deliverable
DoA	Description of Action
EU	European Union
GHG	Greenhouse Gases
IT	Information Technology
IP	Innovation Programme
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
R2R	RIDE2RAIL
T	Task
TC-PA	Travel Companion Personal Assistant
WP	Work Package

2. BACKGROUND

2.1. Shift2Rail context

Shift2Rail is the first European rail initiative to seek focused research and innovation (R&I) and market-driven solutions by accelerating the integration of new and advanced technologies into innovative rail product solutions. Shift2Rail promotes the competitiveness of the European rail industry and meets changing EU transport needs. R&I carried out under this Horizon 2020 initiative develops the necessary technology to complete the Single European Railway Area (SERA).

The delivery of Shift2Rail is based around five Innovation Programmes (IPs); the focus of this report is IP4 – IT solutions for attractive rail services. To become a more attractive option, rail must respond to customer needs to support anytime, anywhere, door-to-door, intermodal journeys encompassing distinct modes of transportation. Rail must achieve interoperability with other transport modes and mobility services, with regions, cities and people engaged in social and economic activities, and with the key elements of the supply chains which can make rail products and services available to those people. In order to achieve this, rail needs to take due advantage of the increasing connectivity of people and objects, the availability of European Global Navigation Satellite Systems (GNSS)-based locations, the advances in cloud computing, big, linked and open data and the propagation of internet and social media. The step towards sharing data needs to be considered and progressively developed, in order to enable service developers to provide connected travellers with the services they need and expect.

2.2. RIDE2RAIL

A key aspect of delivering more attractive services is by delivering end-to-end (or first- and last-mile) travel services that enable rail as their core mode of mobility. This can be challenging in a rural environment, where connectivity to rail is problematic. It is also relevant in urban or peri-urban environments where there may be poorer provision of public transit.

Contributing to Shift2Rail's IP4, RIDE2RAIL's overall objective is to develop an innovative framework for intelligent mobility, facilitating the efficient combination of flexible (ride-sharing) and scheduled transport services (rail, bus, and other public transport services), thus enhancing the performance of the overall mobility system. RIDE2RAIL should, in particular, address the first and last mile problem by offering a wider range of transit options, while harnessing the capacity of single occupancy vehicles, along with existing, or future, demand responsive transit.

RIDE2RAIL aims to integrate multiple (public/private/social) data sets and existing transport platforms for promoting an effective ride sharing practice of citizens, making it a complementary transport mode that extends public transport networks.

The objectives of the RIDE2RAIL project are:

- To develop an innovative framework for intelligent mobility, facilitating efficient combination of flexible and scheduled transport services, integrating real-time information about public transport and ride sharing
- To create a tool that facilitates the comparison and the choice between multiple options/services classified by a set of criteria, for example environmental, travel time, comfort, cost
- To encourage carpooling (and ride sharing acceptance) as complementary for public transport
- To enhance the performance of the overall mobility system, reducing road congestion and environmental impact, reinforcing the mobility offer in rural and low-demand areas
- To combine travel offer classifications and software components, integrating them into existing collective and on-demand transport services
- To induct the access to high-capacity services thanks to easy-to-use multimodal and integrated travel planning, booking, ticketing and payment features
- To design, develop and test in four real demonstrators a set of software components for the IP4 ecosystem, including an advanced Travel Companion and the crowd-based Transport Service Provider
- To produce recommendations for replicability

2.3. Work Package 4 context

Work Package 4 of RIDE2RAIL will implement demonstrations of the RIDE2RAIL solution in four locations – Padua, Italy; Athens, Greece; Brno, Czech Republic; Helsinki, Finland. A critical aspect of these demonstrations is to understand their performance against the aims of the project, and in terms of supporting sustainability actions in these locations. It is therefore necessary to specify targets for the expected performance of the RIDE2RAIL deployment in these locations. These targets are specified as Key Performance Indicators (KPIs). Specifying a complete set of KPIs in a methodical manner allows a full understanding of the impact of RIDE2RAIL, and to define a set of mitigating actions should KPIs not be met during the course of the project. Ultimately, the KPIs will be used to inform the impact analysis for RIDE2RAIL (as calculated in WP5). These impact areas are;

1. increase the number of multi-occupancy vehicle trips, as opposed to single occupancy-vehicle trips
2. increase access to public transit for users in a rural and/or suburban setting
3. contribute to minimising emissions

3. OBJECTIVES

3.1. Deliverable objectives

The aim of this deliverable is to specify a harmonised set of Key Performance Indicators for monitoring the performance of RIDE2RAIL demonstrations. This is to enable the calculation of impact targets as specified in Section 2.2.1 of the DoA, to be conducted in T5.4. A harmonised set of indicators means that a consistent monitoring and measuring approach can be developed across the project, thus ensuring the robustness and reliability of the measures. This will be conducted in WP5 T5.1, to feed the preparation of the monitoring tools in T4.2-4.5, to be delivered in D4.3.

To achieve this aim, a number of objectives were specified;

1. Specify a methodology to capture, analyse and harmonise KPIs
2. Clarify the nature of KPIs, and associated concepts (targets and thresholds)
3. Review potential KPIs as described in preceding documentation (e.g. D4.1)
4. Harmonise and confirm KPIs with demo sites
5. Set targets
6. Capture any additional constraints or concerns that will influence the measurement and management of KPIs as the project progresses

3.2. Scope

The scope of these KPIs is to measure performance associated with the success and performance of the RIDE2RAIL solution, as deployed in the four demonstrator sites, and aggregated measures (e.g. overall single occupancy trips saved) across all four demonstrators that therefore indicate overall success or impact of the RIDE2RAIL solution.

Out of scope for these KPIs are other measures associated with the research impact of RIDE2RAIL (e.g. associated with dissemination or exploitation). New KPIs not already covered in D4.1 were also agreed with WP4 leadership to be out of scope. Also out of scope for this document, but relevant to future tasks (e.g. T5.1), is determining the action plan associated with failure to meet a KPI target.

All KPI targets are based on both technical assumptions and demo site operational conditions as of the time of bilateral calls with demo sites (M12).

4. METHODOLOGY

Figure 1 presents an overview of the methodology applied to capturing KPIs for RIDE2RAIL.

Figure 1 – Methodology

Step 1 involved identifying a framework of important characteristics for analysing and harmonising KPIs. This was conducted by a high level overview of KPIs from D4.1.

Step 2 involved a detailed analysis of D4.1 to identify all specific KPIs, and proposed targets.

Step 3 involved a detailed review of all of D4.1 to identify additional potential targets and any other types of indicator.

Step 4 involved a review of the DOA to both identify project-level KPIs, and to understand the impact types that need to be supported by the KPIs.

Step 5 involved review of Areas of Major Potential Improvement (AMPis) in other Shift2Rail project material to confirm the impacts and therefore the requirements for the KPIs.

Step 6 involved a first harmonisation of all potential KPIs, scoping, and discussion with WP4 lead.

Step 7 involved review with demo site representatives through bi-lateral discussion.

Step 8 involved a second and final harmonisation, which constitutes the final set of KPIs presented in this deliverable.

Step 9 involved analysing gaps and potential future dependencies, constraints and considerations for future tasks that will realise the KPIs.

5. KPI FRAMEWORK

5.1. Definition of a Key Performance Indicator

The section provides a brief presentation of the general characteristics of KPIs. This background helps to shape the requirements for KPIs, and their subsequent measurement.

A Key Performance Indicator is a measurable value that demonstrates how effectively an organisation or project is achieving key objectives. Organisations use KPIs at multiple levels to evaluate their success at reaching targets. High-level KPIs may focus on the overall performance of the organisation or project, typically against significant aims (revenue, capacity, environmental performance), while low-level KPIs may focus on the outputs of specific functions (tickets sold, passenger numbers, time to reach a desired goal with a user interface).

A KPI is usually quantifiable – it can be expressed as a value. Even more qualitative KPIs (such as trust, user experience and satisfaction) are captured as quantified measures. This may be through surveys or questionnaires.

KPIs have a set target. This is a specified value for the KPI that indicates the organisation or project has met an anticipated measure of performance or impact for that particular value.

KPIs are usually associated with an intervention – an action or set of actions that will influence the performance of the KPI, ideally towards the target value.

Each KPI also will have a ‘threshold’ – a minimum value over which indicates the minimum acceptable performance. Limited progress towards the threshold will indicate that remedial action is needed to achieve the demo.

KPIs may also have a baseline - this is an initial value for the KPI. Change, and rate of change from the baseline to the target can indicate the degree of success or performance on the KPI.

The most effective KPIs are SMART (Shahin and Mabod, 2007), where the acronym stands for

Specific – there is a clear objective or target for the KPI

Measurable – there is a clear way of measuring the KPI

Achievable – there is a real prospect of achieving any given target associated with the KPI

Relevant – the KPI relates to a major objective of the organisation or project

Time dependent – there is a set point, or set points, in time where the KPI is measured, and success or performance can be measured against whether the target has been achieved.

When using the SMART acronym, it is clear that not all KPIs that are desirable, no matter how critical they may be, are measurable and therefore suitable. For example, while overall change in global carbon may be the desired outcome of a transport intervention, it is more realistic to measure increased passenger numbers in a Demand Responsive Transit (DRT) service. Thus, KPIs are used to support the later impact analysis (conducted in D5.4).

Table 1 presents how SMART applies to the RIDE2RAIL KPIs.

KPI characteristic	Relevance to RIDE2RAIL
Specific	A KPI must be clearly determined so that its interpretation, and therefore measurement and monitoring, is unambiguous
Measurable	The KPI must be measurable by demo partners. This will be further specified for each KPI in D5.1.
Achievable	The KPI must be associated with a reasonable target, given the demo partner's known conditions and current mobility patterns.
Relevant	The KPI must contribute towards to impact analysis as will be performed in D5.4.
Time dependant	Target must be achievable within the period of demonstrations (typically 90 days)

Table 1 - Relevance of SMART to RIDE2RAIL KPIs

5.2. KPI framework

Having outlined the methodology in Section 4 and some characteristics of KPIs, this section sets out the KPI framework. This framework is used to categorise and describe potential KPIs that are identified in later stages of the methodology.

Initial categories are described in Table 2, below.

Category	Description	Example
ID	Identifying number	1, 2, etc
Name	Identifying name	GHG emissions
Description	Short description of KPI	Measure of greenhouse gas emissions
Source	Source of the KPI	D4.1 table; D4.1 text; R2R DoA; IMPACT-1
Type	Type of KPI	Social; environmental; economic; user
Demo site source	For KPIs in D4.1, originating demo site / partner	Helsinki; Padua; Brno; Athens
Metric	Where known, measure of KPI	Total number of trips
Feasibility	A qualitative assessment of the feasibility of recording KPIs	High (easy to record); Medium (possible to record though may need specific measures or tools); Low (difficult to record) NB this is an indication of whether the KPI can be measured (i.e. whether it is SMART), not whether a target can be achieved

Sustainability type	Category of sustainability improvement anticipated by KPI	Environmental; social; economic; user
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Table 2 - Recorded characteristics of KPIs

These categories were transferred to an excel spreadsheet.

To assist with the first harmonisation, further categories (Table 3) were included for each demo site

Category	Description	Example
Relevance	Whether a given KPI is relevant to a given demonstration site	Yes or no
Target	Target value for that KPI at the demo site, where relevance is yes	3,000 passengers per month

Table 3 - Local characteristics of demo sites

6. HARMONISATION

6.1. Method

The objective of the first harmonisation was to arrive at a candidate set of KPIs that could be used by RIDE2RAIL. This set could then be used for further clarification with demo sites.

The set of characteristics defined in section 5 were used as categories in a spreadsheet. The following documents were then reviewed and, where potential KPIs were found, were added to the spreadsheet with additional data where available.

This involved review of D4.1 demo description tables, D4.1 general text, DoA text covering project overview and specifics of work plans for WP4 and 5, and relevant Shift2Rail material such as outputs from IMPACT-1 project.

These potential KPIs were then de-duplicated, assessed in terms of their compliance with SMART KPIs, and discussed with WP4 leadership team, to arrive at a subset of KPIs.

6.2. Results

The initial analysis of documents arrived 56 potential measures of performance with RIDE2RAIL.

This comprised;

- 29 potential measures from D4.1 demo description tables
- 12 from site snapshot descriptions in D4.1
- 15 from DoA and Shift2Rail material

This list was discussed between UNEW and WP4 Lead FIT. A number of observations were made. First, there were many similar KPIs for demo sites but with slight variations – e.g. number of commuter trips versus number of commuters. Also, similar KPIs varied in their units of measurement. For example, some KPIs were passengers per day, others per year, and others were total for the demo period. These were both aspects of potential KPIs that required harmonisation.

Some of the potential measures were qualitative, relating more to experiential factors (e.g. 'satisfaction'). As these are not directly measurable they were considered out of scope.

Also, some of the measures or indicators were more akin to impacts – results of RIDE2RAIL (e.g. CO2 reduction) rather than performance indicators that could be directly measured in the project. These were considered out of scope for KPIs but will be relevant later for Impact Analysis (T5.4).

Finally, some of the KPIs within the DoA expressed targets for the whole project (i.e. total number of trips conducted with RIDE2RAIL) whereas demo sites had their own specific targets. However, other KPIs were specific to a given demo site (e.g. parking targets for Athens). Therefore three levels of KPIs and targets were identified;

- Whole project KPIs – these are KPIs that apply to the whole project, with whole project targets.
- Cross-demo KPIs – these KPIs match the whole project KPIs, but have demo specific targets. Most or all of the demo sites contribute to whole project KPI targets.
- Local KPIs – these are KPIs and targets that are specific to a demo location.

Based on the analysis and criteria above the following Whole Project / Cross-demo KPIs were defined as

- Number of surveyed users
- Number of surveyed trips
- Trips attracted to Multi-occupancy vehicles
- Trips attracted to Public transit/rail
- Commuters attracted to rideshare
- Total trips with R2R app

Additionally, two location specific KPIs were identified for Athens and five location specific KPIs were identified for Padua.

6.3. Review with Demo Sites and second harmonisation

Task leaders consulted with work package 4 leaders to confirm a format for bi-lateral discussion with each of the demo sites. This included a short presentation on the nature of KPIs and objectives of the work to share with demo sites.

Once a common approach was agreed, a series of bi-lateral meetings was conducted with Padua, Helsinki, Athens and Brno. This involved the presentation of the aims and objectives of the work, presentation of the proposed KPIs and any targets, and discussion around the meaning of KPIs. Demo sites were then asked to send confirmed targets shortly after the meeting.

7. SECOND HARMONISATION AND CONFIRMED KPIS

7.1. Confirmed whole project and cross demo KPIS

Subsequent to discussion with the demo sites, and clarification, the following KPIS were defined (Table 4).

KPI	DEFINITION
KPI#1 Number of RIDE2RAIL app users	Demo site users who download the app and request at least one trip
KPI#2 Number of completed RIDE2RAIL app trips	A completed trip made by a demo site app user
KPI#3 Number of completed multi-occupancy vehicle trips with R2R app	A completed trip made by a demo site app user that involves either rideshare OR Robobus (Helsinki)
KPI#4 Number of completed trips involving public transit/rail with R2R app	A completed multi-modal trip
KPI#5 Number of completed commuter trips with R2R app	A completed trip that is a regular journey (work or education) conducted 4 (including outward or return) or more times a week
KPI#6 Number of completed rural trips with R2R app	A complete trip where one or both origin and destination is from a rural (or suburban) location
KPI#7 Number of Ride2Rail app downloads	Number of times app has been downloaded by unique users

Table 4 - RIDE2RAIL KPI definitions

Table 5 gives the cross-demo targets for each of the KPIS, as specified by demo sites. After discussion with demo sites, initial thresholds have all been set at 50% of target values.

KPI	Athens	Brno	Helsinki	Padua
KPI#1 Number of RIDE2RAIL app users	50	200	50	50
KPI#2 Number of completed RIDE2RAIL app trips	500	4000	400	4500
KPI#3 Number of completed multi-occupancy vehicle trips with R2R app	10	800	200	315
KPI#4 Number of completed trips involving public transit/rail with R2R app	2	100	200	4050
KPI#5 Number of completed commuter trips with R2R app	187	40	240	4050
KPI#6 Number of completed rural trips with R2R app	500	4000	0	3150

Table 5 - Cross-demo KPIS

While there will be downloads (KPI#7) of the app at any given demo site, there are potentially additional downloads from any location from the Apple or Android app store. Therefore, rather than setting cross-demo targets for KPI#7, a single whole project target

was set as the total number of users across the demo site plus an estimate of additional downloads through project dissemination.

This gives the following whole project KPIs (Table 6):

KPIs	Target
KPI#1 Number of RIDE2RAIL app users	350
KPI#2 Number of completed RIDE2RAIL app trips	9400
KPI#3 Number of completed multi-occupancy vehicle trips with R2R app	1325
KPI#4 Number of completed trips involving public transit/rail with R2R app	4352
KPI#5 Number of completed commuter trips with R2R app	4517
KPI#6 Number of completed rural trips with R2R app	7650
KPI#7 Number of R2R app / service downloads	500

Table 6 - whole project KPI targets

7.1.1. Notes and clarifications

Total length of demo period is anticipated at 90 days, however, demo sites may utilise these 90 days in different ways. For example, Brno may have a subset of time (e.g. 2 weeks) with a concerted drive to meet demo targets. For Helsinki, the Robobus will be in operation 2 months out of the 90 days.

Wherever possible, all data will be collected in the app (see 8.3).

Where 2 or more people share a vehicle, each of these will be counted as a multiple-occupancy vehicle trip (i.e. when a driver gives a passenger a lift, both of these will be counted as executing a multi-occupancy vehicle trip).

Trips can be attributed to a multiple categories. In theory, a commuter journey that included a rideshare, and public transit, would be included for all trip categories.

Athens will use incentivisation to attract users to RIDE2RAIL. For Athens, rural will also include peri-urban. This may be the case for other demo sites and will be confirmed in D5.1. Athens targets for KPIs #2, #5 and #6 represent 25 % (i.e. 90 days - the demo duration) of anticipated annual 2000 projected trips with R2R (2000; all trips are rural or peri-urban) and trips with commuters (500).

Brno will target users to include a public transit element to their journey, while additionally encouraging users to engage in ride share.

Due to geography, Helsinki does not anticipate any rural trips.

7.2. Local KPIs

Local KPIs are given for Athens (Table 7), Brno (Table 8), Helsinki (Table 9).

7.2.1. Athens

KPI	Target
KPI#A1 Number of parking spaces at urban gate D. Plakentias	10

KPI#A2 Number of parking spaces at extra-urban Koropi station	5
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Table 7 - Athens local KPIs

7.2.2. Brno

KPI	Target
KPI#B1 Reduction of need for parking spaces	20
KPI#B2 Number of surveyed users attracted to R2R app	60

Table 8 - Brno local KPIs

Brno also proposed a target relating to CO2 (a reduction of 3400Kg CO2). This is best positioned as an impact, and is thus proposed for inclusion in T5.4.

7.2.3. Helsinki

KPI	Target
KPI#3 Number of walk-in trips with the Robobus	200

Table 9 - Helsinki local KPIs

7.3. Observations, constraints and next steps for future tasks

All KPI targets are based on both technical assumptions and demo site operational conditions as of the time of bilateral calls with demo sites (M12). Three specific caveats where highlighted over the setting of targets:

- 1) Achievability of penetration of services, particularly regarding shared travel, given the situation with Covid-19 both now and in the likely aftermath over the next couple of years
- 2) The ability to integrate existing transport service providers (esp. for Robobus @ Helsinki) and therefore ability to predict effectiveness of solution
- 3) For KPI#7 - RIDE2RAIL (or R2R) app or downloads, we note that at this stage that users may not be using a dedicated standalone R2R app, but instead that functionality associated with RIDE2RAIL may be embedded within another app or service (e.g. an app native to a specific demo site). A potential proxy will be downloads of the IP4 TC-PA (Travel Companion - Personal Application) during the period when demos are taking place, measured against a baseline of IP4 TC-PA downloads before. We also note that app downloads may not be through a

conventional ‘app store’ but by a standalone file that is installed directly by users. This will be clarified in D5.1.

These factors have placed conditionality on the targets expressed at this stage, and they may need revision as the situation changes. However, the types of KPI are likely to remain consistent.

On all bilateral calls there was discussion around the challenges of measurement, and the relevance of measurement approaches to being able to be successfully monitored. While these are noted to be a significant factor, this will be the subject of specific enquiry and planning as part of T5.1. In preparation for D5.1, table suggests ways the KPIs could be measured. The final selection will be based on technical feasibility, ease of implementation (technically, for demo sites) and ease of use for participants in demos. A combination of measures may be the most effective way to ensure robust metrics.

KPIs	Example measure
KPI#1 Number of RIDE2RAIL app users	Captured in R2R ecosystem - users with addresses in and around demo site area who have downloaded or registered to service using R2R
KPI#2 Number of completed RIDE2RAIL app trips	Captured in R2R ecosystem - journey request for trip where geospatial data confirms arrival at destination; Captured in microsurvey - user indicates completed trip
KPI#3 Number of completed multi-occupancy vehicle trips with R2R app	Captured in R2R ecosystem - trip that has involved driver / passenger matching, and confirmed with arrival at destination through geospatial data
KPI#4 Number of completed trips involving public transit/rail with R2R app	Captured in R2R ecosystem - trip with origin or destination at PT hub; Captured in microsurvey - user indicates multi-modal trip
KPI#5 Number of completed commuter trips with R2R app	Captured in R2R ecosystem - analysis at end of demo period identifies repeat trips for a user profile; Captured in daily diary - identify commuter trips
KPI#6 Number of completed rural trips with R2R app	Captured in R2R ecosystem - origin or destination for trip is in area designated rural or peri-urban by demo site
KPI#7 Number of R2R app / service downloads	Captured in R2R ecosystem - registration to R2R app / service or to service that encompasses R2R functionality

Table 10 - Example measures of KPIs

All KPIs have focussed on the operational aspects of RIDE2RAIL. This reflected both the nature of KPIs expressed in D4.1 by demo sites and the needs of the impact analysis to be performed in T5.4. Nonetheless, there is a gap in terms of other types of KPIs, that will be covered in forthcoming RIDE2RAIL activities:

User experience KPIs - T5.2 will develop a set of metrics in order to measure usability performance.

Quality/Performance Indicators - at the moment no cross-demo or whole project targets either in terms of Quality of Service (e.g. availability, response times) or in terms of service performance (e.g. number of matches for a rideshare, successfully generated trips) have been defined. These are out of scope as KPIs, but will be raised as potential metrics of app quality in Task 5.2

8. CONCLUSIONS

Understanding the performance and success of RIDE2RAIL requires Key Performance Indicators. The aim of this deliverable is to specify a harmonised set of Key Performance Indicators for monitoring the performance of RIDE2RAIL demonstrations. This is to enable the calculation of impact targets as specified in Section 2.2.1 of the DOA, to be conducted in T5.4. Such indicators must be SMART – specific, measurable, achievable, realistic, and time-dependent. Through analysis of RIDE2RAIL material, and discussion with demo site leaders, seven KPIs have been defined:

- KPI#1 Number of R2R app users
- KPI#2 Number of completed R2R app trips
- KPI#3 Number of completed multi-occupancy vehicle trips with R2R app
- KPI#4 Number of completed trips involving public transit/rail with R2R app
- KPI#5 Number of completed commuter trips with R2R app
- KPI#6 Number of completed rural trips with R2R app
- KPI#7 Number of R2R app / service downloads

Targets have then been assigned for demo sites, thus giving targets for the project as a whole. Additionally, thresholds have been set at 50% of the target values.

A number of local, demo specific KPIs have also been identified, along with local constraints and considerations.

While noting concerns around the achievability of targets given unknowns about Covid-19, and demo site integration, these types of KPI are sufficient to inform the major areas of impact, both for RIDE2RAIL and more widely for Shift2Rail.

The following next steps and dependencies stem from the work described:

- T5.1 will set out the methodology that will capture and monitor each of the KPIs, and will feed the preparation of monitoring tools to be delivered in D4.3. This will involve an analysis of the technical capabilities of RIDE2RAIL to understand where data can be captured implicitly through the app (e.g. origin and destination to determine if a trip was rural), and when other measures such as momentary mobility survey (Cranwell et al., 2015) can be used to supplement the measurement of KPIs. T5.1 will also set out remedial actions should thresholds not be met for each KPIs.
- T5.2 will set out usability and user experience measures. While these are not strictly KPIs, they will give insight and monitoring into key aspects of the RIDE2RAIL app as expressed by demo sites and in D4.1.
- T4.2-4.5 will apply the KPIs within the context of demo evaluations.
- T5.4 will take the KPIs and develop a methodology for calculating impact.

REFERENCES

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